

Mean Amplitudes of Vibration of some Octahedral Hexachloro-molybdates and -tungstates

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Vibrational mean amplitudes of octahedral chloro-molybdates and -tungstates have been reported in the temperature range 0–1000 K using Muller's method of characteristic vibrations and recently proposed spectroscopic data by Creighton and Sinclair. Effect of environments over mean amplitudes for bonded and non-bonded distances of octahedral ions in question were quantitatively studied and bond properties of the two species analysed.

THE mean vibrational amplitudes of octahedral halides had been a subject of investigation by many workers¹⁻⁷. Using the method of characteristic vibrations⁸, Baran^{9,5} has reported significant amount of amplitude data of many octahedral systems. Ferraro^{9,10} studied the force-constants corresponding to mean amplitudes in detail. The dependence of force-constants over some physical properties of atoms involved in bond formation of octahedral structures has been recently analysed by Baker and Sawodny¹¹. As the strength of chemical bond depends on the overlapping of electron clouds of atoms involved¹¹, it looks feasible to study the bond properties and relating it with electronic properties of atoms. As shown by Wilson, the mean amplitudes and force-constants are interrelated¹², and the changes in electron clouds will reflect the changes in mean amplitudes of vibration similar to force-constants. Keeping this in view, the hexachlorides of Mo in its coordination states Mo^{III}, Mo^{IV} and Mo^V and hexachlorides of W, in its coordination states W^{IV} and W^V have been taken as the example for the present aspect of our study. Nearly all the hexachloro-molybdates and -tungstates of the type MCl₆ⁿ⁻ exist in octahedral symmetry (O_h) and hence the principal mean amplitudes would be M–Cl (bonded), Cl...Cl (non-bonded, non-linear), Cl...Cl (non-bonded, linear). These values are computed by using standard procedure of Cyvin¹³ and the Eigen values greater than one have been solved by Muller's formalism¹⁴. The mean amplitude values are calculated from 0 to 1000 K. The data has been correlated with the ionic environment formed by several cations, e.g. (Et₄N), (Et₄N)₂, (K)₃, (NH₄)₃, (Et₄N), (Pr₄N), (Bu₄) and (Et₂NH₂)₂. The vibrational spectrum of the ions in question has recently been reported in all the above mentioned cationic environments by Creighton and Sinclair¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

The available ir and Raman data¹⁵ of MoCl₆²⁻ and WCl₆²⁻ are collected in Table 1. In such centro

TABLE 1—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF HEXACHLORO-MOLYBDATES AND -TUNGSTATES*

Compd.	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	ν_4	ν_5	ν_6
(Et ₄ N)MoCl ₆	356 ^a	191 ^c	327	162	154 ^d	109 ^d
(Et ₄ N) ₂ MoCl ₆	329	189.6 ^c	308	168	154	109 ^c
(Bu ₄ P) ₃ MoCl ₆	329 ^b	—	—	—	—	—
(K) ₃ MoCl ₆	305	154 ^c	268	167	150	106 ^c
			286 ^s	187		
			302 ^{va}			
(NH ₄) ₃ MoCl ₆	305	—	307	—	—	—
(Et ₄ N)WCl ₆	382 ^a	223.7 ^c	332	157	168 ^a	119 ^c
		190 ^c	312			
(Pr ₄ N)WCl ₆	382 ^a	245 ^c	346	159	168 ^a	119 ^c
(Bu ₄ P)WCl ₆	382 ^a	242.5 ^c	344	157	168 ^a	119 ^c
(Et ₂ NH ₂) ₂ WCl ₆	341	197 ^c	293	166	168 ^d	119 ^d
			150			
WCl ₆ ^e	408	312	367	165	206	97

* Ref. 15. ^aSolution in nitromethane. ^bSolution in acetonitrile. ^cComputed. ^dAssumed. ^eJ. C. Evans and Gys Lo, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1968, 26, 147.

symmetric systems, the rule of mutual exclusion is operable, hence three Raman active fundamental modes and two ir active fundamentals are predicted by selection rules. Out of these fundamental vibrations few are missing which could not be observed experimentally. For these vibrations a normal coordinate analysis of the system was performed and missing fundamentals were predicted (ν_3 frequencies). These are also included in Table 1. The missing fundamental ν_2 obeys the rule¹⁶,

$$F_{33}(F_{11}) = (1/3)[F_{11}(A_1g) + 2F_{22}(E_g)]$$

where, F_{11} , F_{22} and F_{33} are force-constants corresponding to ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 frequencies, respectively. Another missing fundamental ν_6 was calculated by Wilson's rule, $\nu_6 = (1/\sqrt{2})\nu_5$. ν_5 in some cases was reported on the basis of our assumption.

Having established all the fundamentals by normal-coordinate analysis, the mean amplitudes are calculated by evaluating Σ -matrices, G -matrices and Δ -values involved in the Cyvin's secular equation¹³, $|\Sigma G^{-1} - \Delta E| = 0$. The three mean amplitude values $(\sigma_r)^{1/2}$, $(\sigma_d)^{1/2}$ and $(\sigma'_d)^{1/2}$ are

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related to the symmetrised mean square amplitudes by the relations,

$$\sigma_r = (1/6)[\Sigma_{11} + 2\Sigma_{22} + 3\Sigma_{33}]$$

$$\sigma_d = (1/3)\Sigma_{11} + (1/6)\Sigma_{22} + (1/2)\Sigma_{33} + (1/8)\Sigma_{44} + (1/8)\Sigma_{55} + (1/8)\Sigma_{66} - (1/2)\Sigma_{34}$$

$$\sigma'_d = (2/3)\Sigma_{11} + (4/3)\Sigma_{22}$$

where, σ_r is the mean square amplitude due to the bonded atom pair M—Cl, σ_d , due to non-bonded atom pair Cl...Cl (non-linear) and σ'_d , due to the non-bonded atom pair Cl...Cl (linear). Their values from $T=0$ to 1000 K are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—MEAN AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION OF SOME HEXACHLORO-MOLYBDATES AND -TUNGSTATES

Temp. K	Distances (Å)		
	M—Cl	Cl...Cl (non-linear)	Cl...Cl (linear)
(Et₄N)MoCl₆			
0	0.048 1	0.086 1	0.064 9
298	0.064 5	0.128 2	0.094 8
500	0.080 3	0.168 4	0.119 4
600	0.087 3	0.183 7	0.130 2
700	0.093 9	0.197 9	0.140 2
800	0.100 0	0.211 2	0.149 6
900	0.105 9	0.223 8	0.158 5
1000	0.111 5	0.235 7	0.166 9
(Et₄N)₂MoCl₆			
0	0.049 2	0.087 0	0.065 6
298	0.066 6	0.134 2	0.096 2
500	0.083 1	0.169 8	0.121 4
600	0.090 4	0.190 2	0.132 4
700	0.097 0	0.199 2	0.142 5
800	0.103 7	0.212 9	0.152 2
900	0.109 8	0.225 6	0.161 2
1000	0.115 6	0.237 6	0.169 7
(K)₂MoCl₆			
0	0.051 5	0.090 5	0.071 8
298	0.077 6	0.142 3	0.115 0
500	0.097 7	0.227 2	0.146 2
600	0.106 5	0.197 0	0.071 8
700	0.114 7	0.212 3	0.115 0
800	0.122 4	0.234 8	0.146 3
900	0.129 6	0.240 2	0.159 7
1000	0.136 5	0.253 0	0.172 2
(Et₄N)WCl₆			
0	0.043 7	0.077 3	0.060 5
	0.045 8	0.078 4	0.064 5
298	0.056 7	0.119 3	0.083 0
	0.062 3	0.150 3	0.094 4
500	0.070 2	0.150 9	0.103 7
	0.077 8	0.153 8	0.119 0
600	0.076 2	0.164 6	0.112 9
	0.084 6	0.167 8	0.129 7
700	0.081 9	0.177 4	0.121 5
	0.091 0	0.177 7	0.139 7
800	0.087 3	0.189 3	0.129 6
	0.097 0	0.196 4	0.149 1
900	0.092 4	0.200 6	0.137 2
	0.102 7	0.204 4	0.157 9
1000	0.097 2	0.211 2	0.144 4
	0.108 2	0.211 6	0.166 3

(Table 1 contd.)

(Pr₄N)WCl₆			
0	0.040 8	0.076 6	0.058 4
298	0.053 8	0.117 8	0.077 5
500	0.066 3	0.149 0	0.096 4
600	0.071 9	0.162 5	0.104 9
700	0.077 2	0.175 0	0.112 8
800	0.082 3	0.186 8	0.120 2
900	0.087 0	0.197 9	0.127 2
1000	0.091 6	0.208 5	0.133 9

(Bu₄P)WCl₆			
0	0.042 6	0.076 8	0.058 7
298	0.054 2	0.118 3	0.078 1
500	0.066 7	0.149 6	0.097 2
600	0.072 4	0.169 2	0.105 7
700	0.077 8	0.175 8	0.113 7
800	0.079 0	0.187 6	0.121 2
900	0.087 7	0.198 8	0.128 3
1000	0.092 2	0.209 4	0.135 0

(Et₄NH₂)₂WCl₆			
0	0.046 5	0.078 9	0.064 4
298	0.063 3	0.121 6	0.093 0
500	0.079 0	0.154 0	0.117 0
600	0.086 0	0.168 0	0.127 6
700	0.092 6	0.181 1	0.137 4
800	0.098 7	0.193 2	0.146 6
900	0.104 5	0.204 7	0.155 2
1000	0.100 0	0.215 6	0.163 5

WCl₆^a			
298	0.051 2	0.111 5	0.064 9

^aH. S. Singh, N. K. Sanyal and A. N. Pandey, *Curr. Sci.*, 1969, 38, 108.

All the values increase with the increase of temperature and the general trend, $\sigma_d > \sigma'_d > \sigma_r$, is valid as in the case of other hexahalides. The variation in bonded mean amplitudes with respect to the changes in the cationic environment in the case of MoCl_6^{2-} indicates that more bulky the cationic environment, the greater is the mean amplitude. This means that the electron-pair forming the bond Mo—Cl, is influenced by the electron clouds of the environmental cation resulting in a change in the bond strength of Mo—Cl. This is also true in the case of frequencies of the same octahedral ion present in the different cationic environments. It means clearly that the trend of variation in the frequencies as well as amplitudes of vibration would depend on the bulk of cations and their polarising powers. However, in the case of WCl_6^{2-} this trend is not accurately followed. It is also observed that the more bulky the cationic environment, the less are the values of mean amplitudes meaning thereby that W—Cl bond is stronger for all the WCl_6^{2-} ions which are attached with heavier cationic environment. Based on the present study of mean amplitudes of vibration at different temperatures ranging from $T=0$ to 1000 K, the order of stability of W—Cl bond is just opposite to that of Mo—Cl bond in various MoCl_6^{2-} species.

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